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Judeo-Christian Ethics in Medicine

A critical analysis

Abstract

Physicians are increasingly confronted with ethical challenges in their daily work in clinics and practices. Advances in medical technology have opened up new possibilities for action and intervention at the beginning and end of life, which challenge not only our moral judgment but also our understanding of ourselves as human beings.

Basic aspects

More and more frequently, the question arises whether everything that would be medically possible should actually be carried out. At the same time, our society is characterized by a pluralism of values and life concepts, so that ethical challenges can rarely be based on a generally shared consensus of values. This raises the question: Is the search for a social consensus really purposeful? Or must ethics and morality remain an inner process in the individual? The Bible does not know the word "consensus" in today's sense. Rather, the Holy Book promotes clear points of view and the willingness to live with differences. Consensus is not a Judeo-Christian concept, but a secular

product of modern times. Or, as Margaret Thatcher made clear, "Consensus is the process of abandoning all beliefs, principles, values, and policies in search of something in which no one believes, but to which no one objects; the process of avoiding the very issues that have to be solved, merely because you cannot get agreement on the way ahead. What great cause would have been fought and won under the banner: I stand for consensus?" This sharp opinion is completely covered by the essence of the Holy Bible. The Messiah did not advise opening a discussion circle after the first slap in the face, but to stand firm. This aspect is pathetically misinterpreted by naive pacifists to this day.^{Matthew 5:39} More important is the aspect that the increasing economization of many health care systems is provoking intra-personal ethical conflict situations. Therefore, medical ethics is actually as old as medicine as a written discipline. As early as ancient Greece, physicians committed themselves in the so-called 'Hippocratic Oath' to benefit the patient, to do him no harm and to maintain confidentiality. This moral obligation on the part of physicians is rooted in the archetypal basic situation of need and help, which has always characterized the doctor-patient relationship: a person in need due to illness will only be able to entrust himself to a physician if he can rely on him to take certain moral principles into account, in particular that he will put his own interests behind those of the patient.^{7,8,11,12} The physician himself is part of the art of healing, he has been ever since: If you have no defender for your case, there is no remedy for your sores, and no healing for you.^{Jeremiah 30:13}

What is new, however, is the increasing complexity of ethical challenges, for which the traditional medical ethos often offers only insufficient orientation in a world which abandons religious beliefs more and more. Not only technological innovations, but also new structures of health care and expanded tasks of medicine constantly require a new reflection and discussion of ethical questions. Since the 1970s, the ethical boundaries of what is medically possible have no longer been discussed solely by the actors, the researchers and physicians, but have increasingly been systematically researched and taught in medical and clerical institutions - mostly by secular moralists, which is a path towards arbitrariness and chaos.^{Matthew 23:25} Such "ethical" reflection has thus found its own place in the sciences; the medical ethos is supplemented and expanded by medical ethics. It is not limited to the medical profession, but includes all actors in the health care system. Beyond teaching and research, medical ethics has taken on an explicit and increasingly professional form in various advisory services. In simpler terms, the health care industry has occupied and annexed the question of ethics and morality in applied medicine.^{2,7,11,14, Matthew 21:12-14}

Political decision-makers both within and outside the health care system are increasingly drawing on medical ethics expertise, but from whom? The review of research projects involving human subjects by ethics committees can now look back on a long and tradition. Has it ever been questioned or challenged? No, it has not. In contrast, "ethical counseling services" in hospitals and other health care facilities, which provide

support in ethically difficult questions of care for sick people, are a comparatively recent development. So there is an effort to make the major questions of ethics into something mundane and thus trivialize it. These 'clinical ethics consultations'" are an attempt to implement ethical reflection in the everyday life of health care in an explicit, structured and methodically supported way and to support the involved actors in the perception of their moral responsibility. It is capable of illuminating, but not replacing, the ethical judgment of decision-makers in the field. However, the responsibility for decision-making inevitably remains with the actors involved - and they are not moral theologians, not in any sense. So this whole approach is little more than a bad joke.

An essential goal of ethical reflection in medicine is to work out ethically well-founded solutions in difficult decision-making situations. However, this raises the question of which grounds should guide medical ethics: Which normative points of orientation should be decisive for ethical decisions in medicine? While not one atheist ethical theory has been able to establish itself as the only correct one in moral philosophy, a more practical approach has been developed for the medical field in the form of "principle-oriented medical ethics", which - at least in the Western world - is widely accepted and is applied in all areas of medicine. The approach abandons the claim of a comprehensive ethical theory and is oriented instead on four widely consensual "middle" principles that are compatible with various moral theories. The principles are derived (reconstructed) from everyday moral beliefs and brought into a coherent context. One therefore also speaks of a "reconstructive" or "coherentist" approach to reasoning. Or, to put it more simply, it is nothing but worldly chatter.

Nevertheless, the following four principles of medical ethics define the fundamental moral obligations of physicians and other health care personnel. They thus provide a binding orientation in difficult ethical decision-making situations:

- The "principle of beneficence" obligates all health care professionals to promote the patient's well-being in the best possible way, i.e., to select those measures that offer the greatest benefit to the patient. Beneficial measures are generally those that improve the patient's life expectancy and/or quality of life. Sounds good, but is almost impossible to actually apply in everyday life. No doctor in this world is trained accordingly, unless he/she asks for it. But that is only a vanishingly small minority. No wonder the rate of alcoholics and illicit drug addicts among physicians has reached alarming proportions.
- The "principle of nonmaleficence" obligates the physician, if possible, not to harm the patient through the therapeutic efforts. Often, however, the physician can only help the patient effectively if he or she can risks and burdens to the patient's health (just think of the inhuman oncological or some intensive care treatments). In this case, careful consideration of the benefits and harms for the patient is necessary. However,

this issue is not new: "And had endured much [suffering] at the hands of many physicians. She had spent all that she had and was not helped at all, but instead had become worse."^{Mark 5:26} But what or who helped the patient? "For she thought, "If I just touch [Jesus'] clothing, I will get well."^{Mark 5:28} "And immediately the flow of blood dried up, and she felt in her body that she was healed of her disease."^{Mark 5:29} As so often in the Holy Bible, this testimony stands as *pars pro toto*. The woman was not healed by the most expensive doctors, but through the Messiah, who had nothing in Him but infinite benevolence. This is closer to the everyday experience of modern physicians than thick books on ethics lacking any trace of faith. Trust, unbreakable trust is just as central as unconditional benevolence and empathy on the part of the physician. This inner attitude makes healing possible. This does not stand in the way of modern medicine with its high-end devices, except in one point: the inner attitude of the medical professional must be more important than the device, and the doctor-patient contact must be sincerely benevolent.

- According to the "principle of respect for autonomy", only those measures may be carried out to which the patient has given his or her own consent after being adequately informed (so-called "informed consent"). The principle of autonomy includes not only freedom of decision, but also the obligation to actively support the patient in his or her decision-making process, thus enabling the patient to make a self-determined decision about the measures to be carried out. The conditions of "informed consent" are fulfilled when the patient is cognitively capable of making a decision, has received sufficient information and understood it, makes a decision voluntarily and finally gives his or her consent to the measure. In addition consent can only be considered as valid if the physician discloses his knowledge, conflicts of interest, gains through the planned therapy - and, something that most miss, to inform the patient honestly about the many knowledge gaps every medical doctor has. Only then we can call it truly an "informed consent."^{Proverbs 1:10}
- The "principle of justice" looks beyond the individual patient and calls for a fair distribution of benefits and burdens in the health care system. These ethical questions of distributive justice are likely to gain further importance in the coming years due to the increasing discrepancy between what is medically possible and what is financially feasible. At its core, justice demands equal treatment of patients: Equal cases should be treated equally, and unequal cases should be treated unequally only insofar as they exhibit morally relevant differences. What are morally relevant differences in individual cases often poses interpretive difficulties. However, from a strictly biblical perspective the decisive motive should not be equality but justice. The topos of equality is a modern invention, justice, however, is consistent with the Judeo-Christian theology.^{Deuteronomy 16:20}

Conclusion

Every contact of patient and doctor is a true *momento mori*⁵ of the highest intensity. Doctors and patients cannot escape the question of the finiteness of human life. Therefore, how physicians cope with this dimension of their profession is to be investigated in a separate study. Many patients, on the other hand, cope with this overwhelming context by making their doctor a kind of demigod with a stethoscope, that is, by exaggerating him or her inappropriately. Others devalue the doctor from the very beginning, and a third group avoids visiting a doctor whenever possible. The underlying fear is always the same, the unconscious awareness of mortality, which crystallizes in the doctor's visit as a *momento mori*. Neither the doctors nor the patients are aware of this fact in daily practice. However, there can be no sustainable rules for a life-affirming and benevolent ethics in medicine as long as this aspect remains suppressed.

Conflicts of interest

none of relevance

References

1. The Oxford Handbook of Early Christian Biblical Interpretation. (2019). United Kingdom: OUP Oxford
2. Ethics and Values in Health Care Management. (1998). UK, Routledge
3. Yee, G. A. (2021). Towards an Asian American Biblical Hermeneutics: An Intersectional Anthology. United States: Wipf and Stock Publishers
4. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/de/worterbuch/englisch/memento-mori>
5. Moyise, S. (2013). Introduction to Biblical Studies. United Kingdom: Bloomsbury Publishing
6. Lemche, N. P. (2014). Biblical Studies and the Failure of History: Changing Perspectives 3. United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis
7. Miles, S. H. (2005). The Hippocratic Oath and the Ethics of Medicine. UK, Oxford University Press
8. Boer, R. (2016). Secularism and Biblical Studies. United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis
9. The Oxford Handbook of Biblical Studies. (2006). United Kingdom: OUP Oxford
10. Gorman, G. E., Gorman, L., Matthews, D. N., Gratch, B. (1984). Theological and Religious Reference Materials: General resources and biblical studies. United Kingdom: Greenwood Press

11. Zaidi, S. H. (2013). *Ethics in Medicine*. Springer International Publishing.
12. Lemche, N. P. (2014). *Biblical Studies and the Failure of History: Changing Perspectives 3*. United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis
13. *International Review of Biblical Studies, Volume 49 2002-2003*. (2004). NL, Brill
14. *Medical Ethics*. (1997), UK, Jones and Bartlett Publishers
15. Plumtre, E.H. (1870). *Biblical Studies*. United Kingdom: (n.p.).
16. *Jewish Theology*. (2020). United States: Library of Alexandria.
17. *Understanding Jewish Theology: Classical Issues and Modern Perspectives*. (1973). United States: Ktav Publishing House
18. Ellis, M. H. (2004). *Toward a Jewish theology of liberation : the challenge of the 21st century*. United States: Baylor University Press
19. Harvey, R. (2009). *Mapping Messianic Jewish Theology: A Constructive Approach*. United Kingdom, Paternoster
20. Walker, R., Nixon, L. L., Paola, F. A. (2009). *Medical Ethics and Humanities*. USA, Jones & Bartlett Learning.
21. Moffic, E., Morris, L. A., Plevan, W., Sommer, B. D., Stern, E., Beit-Halachmi, R. S., Marmur, M., Shapiro, M. B., Balin, C. B., Lopatin, A., Cosgrove, E. J., Sax, B., Kalmanofsky, J., Rose, O. N., Appelbaum, T., Bronstein, D. M., Gordon, J. Artson, B. S., Jacobson-Maisels, J., Held, S., Kelman, N. (2012). *Jewish Theology in Our Time: A New Generation Explores the Foundations and Future of Jewish Belief*. United States: Long Hill Partners Inc.
22. Ladouceur, P. (2019). *Modern Orthodox Theology: Behold, I Make All Things New*. United Kingdom: Bloomsbury Publishing.
23. *American Theological Inquiry, Volume One, Issue One: A Biannual Journal of Theology, Culture, and History*. (2008). United States: Wipf & Stock Publishers
24. Shepard, D. J. (2014). *Panentheism Addressing Volume 1-3 Guide / Reference*. (n.p.): CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform
25. Cooper, J. W. (2006). *Panentheism--The Other God of the Philosophers: From Plato to the Present*. United States: Baker Publishing Group.

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